

Neon Ghosts with ggplot2

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2025-10-31

Ever wanted to make a haunted house in R? Here's a quick and fun way to conjure up a whole gang of neon ghosts using ggplot2. Each ghost is a little different — some tall, some stout, all a bit wobbly—thanks to a shape generator that randomizes their size and wiggle.

The plotting function layers up neon glows for the outline, eyes, and mouth, then adds a faint fill and solid black features for that classic ghostly look. Try running it a few times to see what kind of spectral friends you get!

```
library(ggplot2)
library(scales)

#' Ghost plotting function
#' @param ghost_df Data frame with x and y coordinates of the ghost shape
#' @param ghost_color Color of the ghost (default is neon green)
#' @return ggplot object of the ghost
plot_simple_ghost <- function(ghost_df, ghost_color = "#39FF14") {
  x_center <- mean(range(ghost_df$x))
  y_top <- max(ghost_df$y)
  y_bottom <- min(ghost_df$y)
  ghost_height <- y_top - y_bottom
  ghost_width <- diff(range(ghost_df$x))

  # Eyes
  eye_y <- y_bottom + 0.7 * ghost_height
  eye_x <- x_center + c(-0.06, 0.06) * ghost_width
  eyes <- data.frame(x = eye_x, y = rep(eye_y, 2))

  # Mouth: several waves
  mouth_width <- ghost_width * 0.4
  mouth_x <- seq(x_center - 0.3 * mouth_width, x_center + 0.3 * mouth_width, length.out = 80)
  mouth_y <- y_bottom + 0.55 * ghost_height + sin(seq(0, 7 * pi, length.out = 80)) * 0.04 * g
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mouth <- data.frame(x = mouth_x, y = mouth_y)

# 8 neon glow layers
glow_layers <- data.frame(
  linewidth = c(12, 10, 8, 6, 4.5, 3, 2, 1),
  alpha = c(0.04, 0.06, 0.09, 0.13, 0.18, 0.25, 0.35, 0.5)
)

p <- ggplot() +
  geom_polygon(
    data = ghost_df, aes(x, y),
    fill = ghost_color, alpha = 0.15, color = NA
  )

# Glow layers for outline, eyes, and mouth
for(i in seq_len(nrow(glow_layers))) {
  p <- p +
    geom_polygon(
      data = ghost_df, aes(x, y),
      fill = NA, color = scales::alpha(ghost_color, glow_layers$alpha[i]),
      linewidth = glow_layers$linewidth[i]
    ) +
    geom_point(
      data = eyes, aes(x, y),
      color = scales::alpha(ghost_color, glow_layers$alpha[i]),
      size = glow_layers$linewidth[i] * 1.1
    ) +
    geom_path(
      data = mouth, aes(x, y),
      color = scales::alpha(ghost_color, glow_layers$alpha[i]),
      linewidth = glow_layers$linewidth[i]
    )
}

# Solid black mouth and eyes
p <- p +
  geom_path(
    data = mouth, aes(x, y),
    color = "black", linewidth = 1.2
  ) +
  geom_point(
    data = eyes, aes(x, y),

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        color = "black",
        size = 1.2
    )

# Fix aspect ratio and theme
p +
  coord_fixed(
    xlim = c(-4, 4),
    ylim = c(-3, 8),
    expand = TRUE
  ) +
  theme_void() +
  theme(
    plot.background = element_rect(fill = "black", color = NA),
    panel.background = element_rect(fill = "black", color = NA)
  )
}

#' Generate a random ghost shape
#' @param seed Optional seed for reproducibility
#' @return Data frame with x and y coordinates of the ghost shape
ghost_shape <- function(seed = NULL) {
  if (!is.null(seed)) set.seed(seed)
  width <- sample(seq(0.5, 3, length.out = 6), 1)
  height <- sample(1:6, 1)
  x <- seq(-1, 1, length.out = 100) * width
  amp <- runif(1, 0.15, 0.28)
  freq <- sample(3:7, 1)
  phase <- runif(1, 0, 2*pi)
  y_top <- sqrt(1 - (x/width)^2) * height + runif(1, -0.03, 0.03)
  y_bottom <- -0.5 * height + sin(seq(0, freq * pi, length.out = 100) + phase) * amp * height
  data.frame(
    x = c(x, rev(x)),
    y = c(y_top, rev(y_bottom))
  )
}

ghost_shape() |>
  plot_simple_ghost(ghost_color = "#39FF14")

ghost_shape() |>
  plot_simple_ghost(ghost_color = "#FF6EC7")

```

```
ghost_shape() |>  
  plot_simple_ghost(ghost_color = "#1E90FF")
```